

Some Photocycloadditions and Photorearrangements

R. P. GANDHI, MRS. S. GARG and S. M. MUKHERJI,

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, KURUKSHETRA (Haryana).

A succinct account of our work on photocycloadditions involving 1, 4-quinones, non-benzenoid aromatics, coumarins, carbostyrils, acetylenes, olefins, and on photoreorganisations in steroidal enamides is presented giving critical references from the literature.

OF the areas of research interest to the Organic Photochemist, which have witnessed intense activity in the past decade, have been the study of photocycloadditions (involving a combination of a variety of unsaturates) and of intramolecular photoreorganisations in a multitude of mono- and bifunctional molecular species. The photocycloadditions have mostly included systems such as mono-olefins, diolefins, acetylenes, aromatic compounds, carbonyl compounds, thioketones etc., and the earlier results have been summarised in a few recent articles¹⁻³. In this paper, we record some of our own contributions, during the past five years, in this field. However, in writing this, emphasis has been placed more on the type of cycloadditions that have been found to occur (and on the nature of the cycloadducts) while citing only relevant collateral references from the literature.

Photocycloaddition of Dimethyl acetylene-dicarboxylate (DMAD) to Non-benzenoid Aromatics and 2, 3-Dihydropyran.

In an unsensitised photolysis of a mixture of DMAD and furan, acceleration of the thermal reaction* leading to a 1:2 adduct (I) was observed.⁴ The preference for the exo-exo expression (I) over the alternate endo-endo formulation (II) was indicated by the failure of (I) to photocyclise to a cage. The photoaddition of DMAD to pyrrole (using unfiltered light), however, led to the formation of 1H-3, 4-dicarbomethoxyazepine (IV)⁶ presumably through the intermediate 2+2 π electron adduct (III); this manner of addition is reminiscent of the photoformation of dimethyl cyclooctatetraene-dicarboxylate from benzene and DMAD.⁷ The alternate expression (VII)^{6f, 8} for the 1H-azepine which would have fol-

lowed through the intermediates 7-aza-bicycloheptadiene (V) and the quadricyclane (VI) was not upheld by its NMR and other spectra.

The photoformation of IV** is sensitised by benzophenone. However, when in a photoreaction of DMAD and pyrrole, air was not excluded, and light was not filtered, then in addition to IV, an oxygen adduct of the tetramer (VIII) of DMAD was formed. The formation of VIII has also been reported by LeGoff and LaCount¹² through photoisomerisation of the thermal tetramer (IX) of DMAD.

An unsensitised photoreaction of N-methylpyrrole with DMAD led only to the isolation of an earlier-known thermal adduct¹³. The addition of DMAD to dimethyl-furazan (using direct light, and under conditions of benzophenone sensitisation) did not succeed.

*In an earlier paper⁵ describing the formation of the Diels-Alder adduct (I), no stereochemical details of I have been given out.

**Since no other method for the obtention of 1H-azepines is yet known, special interest attaches to this reaction in view of the recent predictions⁹ of marked polyene character of 1H-azepine and of the expectations of anti-aromaticity in a planar configuration in this system^{10,11}.

The photoreaction of DMAD with the unsymmetrical cyclic olefin i.e., 2, 3-dihydropyran led to a single 1:1 addition compound (X)¹⁴. From NMR couplings, the preference for conformation (XI) over the alternate conformation (XIa) for the adduct (X) was indicated. In a recent report¹⁵ on the photoaddition of diphenylacetylene to 2, 3-dihydropyran, a similar conformation has been concluded from the X-ray diffraction measurements on the adduct.

Photocycloadditions involving 1, 4-Naphthoquinones

While the photoreaction of 1,4-naphthoquinone with 2, 3-dimethylbutadiene (at 0° with light 7400 m μ) has been reported¹⁶ to produce a mixture of 7-iso-propenyl-7-methylbenzo [c] bicyclo [4, 2, 0]-octane-2, 5-dione (a cyclobutane) and a 2+4 π electron addition compound i.e., benzo [e] cyclohex-2-en-4-one-spiro-2'-(2', 3'-dihydro-4', 5'-dimethyl-pyran) (a dihydropyran), the photoaddition of cycloheptatriene to 1, 4-naphthoquinone and 2-methoxy-1, 4-naphthoquinone at room temperature (using light filtered through pyrex) led to the formation of a typical oxetanes (XII)¹⁷ to the exclusion of cyclobutane or dihydropyran.

2-Amino-1,4-naphthoquinone, however, upon irradiation in presence of cyclopentadiene (in a pyrex reactor) formed, in addition to a cyclobutane, the cage diketone (XIV)¹⁸ by an intramolecular photocycloaddition of the thermal 2+4 π electron addition compound (XIII). The formation of the cage (XIV) is interesting, involving as it does, an intramolecular

2+6 π electron 1, 2 addition in which the 6 π system of the benzene ring is not regenerated.¹⁹

Photodimerisation of some Coumarin Derivatives

The photodimerisation of 2, 4-dimethyl-coumalin and coumarin has drawn some special interest. While the former, in an unsensitised photolysis, produces 1, 2 and 1, 4 dimers,²⁰ the latter displays different modes of bond union in its direct and photosensitised dimerisation.²¹ To learn more about the manner of photoautoaddition in substituted coumarins, we studied the dimerisations¹⁸ (under conditions of benzophenone sensitisation) in 4-methyl-umbelliferone acetate (XVa), 4-methyl-umbelliferone (XVb), 4-methyl-coumarin (XVc), 3-methylcoumarin (XVd), umbelliferone (XVe) and in 4-methyl-carbostyryl (XVIIa) and 1, 4-dimethyl-carbostyryl (XVIIb). The cis-anti-cis expressions (XVI) and (XVIII) are at present based on the mechanistic considerations²² involved in the sensitised photodimerisations. However, XVb upon irradiation gave, in addition to XVIb, a small amount of a thermally unstable dimer for which an all-cis expression (XIX) has been projected, and which may have formed through the intervention of the singlet excited coumarin (XVb) resulting from direct light absorption.²²

The direct NMR determination of stereochemistry, around the cyclobutanes in the above dimers proved impossible as their 100 MHz spectra (even in DMSO-d₆) did not show up any magnetic non-equivalence of the cyclobutane protons†. The NMR spectra (in DMSO-d₆) of the cyclobutane-diester (XX) derived from the dimers (XVIIb and XVIIc) were also not conclusive.¹⁸

In the benzophenone-sensitised dimerisations of the methyl-coumarins (XVa and XVc) were also produced the 1:1 adducts (XXIa and XXIc respectively). The tert.-alcohols (XXI) presumably result through hydrogen abstraction by triplet excited benzophenone from the 4-methyl group in (XVa) and (XVc) with subsequent linking up of the two radicals in each case.

From the extent of conversions of the various coumarin derivatives into their dimers, realised under comparable conditions (TABLE I), the activity of

†A recent report reveals that, in liquid SO₂ solvent, the cyclobutane protons of some coumarin and carbostyryl dimers do show up as magnetically non-equivalent²³.

TABLE I

Compound	Wattage of the lamp	Concentration gm. mole/litre	Period of Irradiation (hrs)	% Conversion
1. 4-Methyl-Coumarin	80	0.25	26	68%
2. 3-Methyl-Coumarin	80	0.25	32	10%
3. Umbelliferone	80	0.22	26	21%
4. 3-Carboethoxy-Coumarin	80	0.25	26	0%
5. 4-Methyl-Umbelliferone	125	0.25	29	33% XVIb + 16% XIX
6. 4-Methyl-Carbostyryl	125	0.16	21	54%
7. 1, 4-Dimethyl-Carbostyryl	125	0.12	25	13%
8. 4-Methyl-Umbelliferone acetate	125	0.48	61	74%

3,4-double bonds in these compounds towards photoautoadditions can be roughly gauged.

Amongst 4-methyl-umbelliferone, 4-methyl-coumarin, 3-methyl-coumarin and umbelliferone (whose irradiations were all done with 80 watts lamps except in case of 4-methyl-umbelliferone where a 125 watts lamp was used for similar period), the highest yields were attainable with 4-methyl-coumarin (68%) and that

the yield decreases in the order, 4-methyl-umbelliferone (33% XVIb + 16% XIX), umbelliferone (21%), 3-methyl-coumarin (10%). The activity thus seems to increase with the introduction of 4-methyl-substituent or to decrease with a 7-hydroxyl-substituent in coumarin. Again, the 3-substituent lowers the reactivity; with 3-methyl-coumarin, the yield being as low as 10%, while nothing happens when 3-carboethoxy-coumarin is photolysed under similar (as well as more forcing) conditions. In the case of 4-methyl- and 1, 4-dimethyl-carbostyryl, the conversions realised under comparable conditions are indicative of a faster reaction with the former (54%) than with the latter (13%).

Addition of Photochemically-generated Ethoxy-carbonyl-nitrene to Steroid Double Bonds.

A great deal of speculation exists on the stereochemical consequences of the multiplicity of the electronic state of nitrenes from which they enter into addition/insertion reactions.²⁴ We have observed²⁵ that the photochemically-generated ethoxy-carbonyl-nitrene adds onto the 4, 5 double bond in testosterone acetate in a stereospecific manner to produce N-ethoxycarbonyl-4 α , 5 α -imino-3-oxo-androstan-17 β -ol-17-acetate (XXII)†.

†In a similar reaction on 17 α -hydroxy-progesterone, rapid photofragmentation of the C₁₇ substituent occurred to produce androsten-3, 17-dione²⁶.

However, on the 16, 17 double bond in 16-dehydro-pregnenolone acetate, the ethoxy-carbonyl-nitrene added on to give both the stereoisomeric aziridinyl-ketones (XXIII) and (XXIV). In addition, the aziridine (XXV) and the carbamate (XXVI) (an insertion product) were also formed.²⁷ The stereospecific formation of (XXII) in the above photoaddition is perhaps a consequence of the steric influence of the C₁₀-methyl during the nitrene addition to the 4, 5 double bond in testosterone acetate. §

Photorearrangements in Steroidal Enamides

Though the photoanilide rearrangement is now well documented^{28, 29}, the photochemistry of enamides has received scant attention. However, a few reports have recently appeared on phototransformations in the bicyclic enamide i.e., 1-methyl-1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8-octahydro-2-quinolone which, upon irradiation in methanol or amines, furnishes derivatives of 3-(2'-oxocyclohexyl)-propionic acid (presumably through a ketene intermediate)³⁰, and in acyclic enamides^{32, 31} which, by an intramolecular acyl migration, produce vinylogous amides. Fischer³³ has observed the photo-conversion of N-phenyl-propiolactam into an aza-tetralone. We find that the manner of photochemical change in 4-aza- Δ^5 -3-oxo-steroids (which we have studied at some length) shows remarkable dependence on the nature of the substituent at C₄. Whereas the N-phenyl-lactam (XXVII) underwent, upon direct irradiation in THF, ring A enlargement to produce (XXVIII)³⁴, the 4-benzyl-lactam (XXIX) rearranged, by migration of the benzyl group

from C₄ to C₆, to the enamide (XXX)³⁵ and the 4-methyl-lactam (XXXI) was converted, under comparable conditions, into the aziridinyl-ketone (XXXII).¹⁸ The conversions XXVII→XXVIII and XXXI→XXXII presumably involve initial O=C—N bond cleavage in (XXVII) and (XXXI) to produce the respective diradicals A and A' which after electronic reorganisations as shown collapse respectively to (XXVIII) and (XXXII). In the transformation XXIX→XXX, initial loss of the benzyl radical (which derives stabilisation through resonance) from the photoexcited enamide (XXIX) is envisaged.

§The stereochemical assignments in the obtained steroidal aziridines were made from a detailed analysis of their various spectra including the ORD and CD measurements^{25, 27}.

The imide (XXXIII), however, rearranged, in THF with unfiltered light, to the primary amide (XXXIV).³⁶ Of particular interest in the conversion

XXXIII→XXXIV is the involvement of the seven-membered cyclic transition state in an intramolecular hydrogen transfer (C→D). The loss of CO observed presently (B→C) in the liquid phase photolysis of an amide is, however, unexceptional.³⁷ The above observation of the rearrangement XXXIII→XXXIV contrasts markedly with that of Witkop³⁸ on the photoconversion of dihydrothymidine to N₁-deoxy-ribosyl-N₁-n-propyl-urea, which sequence involves intramolecular hydrogen transfer through the usual six-membered cyclic transition state.

The photorearrangements of 4-aryl-4-aza- Δ^5 -3-oxo-steroids show sensitisation by benzophenone¹⁸ suggesting involvement of the triplet excited state of the enamide functionality in their reactions.

References :

1. D. C. NECKERS, 'Mechanistic Organic Chemistry', Reinhold, New York, 1967, p. 98.
2. L. L. MULLER and J. HAMER, '1,2-Cycloaddition Reactions', Interscience, New York, 1967, p. 111.
3. D. R. ARNOLD in 'Advances in Photochemistry', (Ed.) W. A. NOYES, G. S. HAMMOND and J. N. PITTS, Interscience, New York, 1968, Vol. 6, p. 301.
4. R. P. GANDHI and V. K. CHADHA, *Chem. Comm.*, 1968, 552.
5. O. DIELS and K. ALDER, *Annalen*, 1931, 490, 243.
6. R. P. GANDHI and V. K. CHADHA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 305.
7. D. BRYCE-SMITH and J. E. LODGE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 695.
8. H. PRINZBACH, R. FUCHS and R. KITZING, *Angew. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 67.
9. R. W. SCHMIDT, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1962, 45, 1982.
10. R. BRESLOW, J. BROWN and J. GAJEWSKI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 89, 4383.
11. L. A. PAQUETTE, D. E. KUHLA, J. H. BARRETT and R. J. HALUSKA, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1969, 34, 2866.
12. E. LEGOFF and R. B. LACOUNT, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1967, 2333.
13. R. M. ACHESON and J. M. VERNON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 1148.
14. R. P. GANDHI and V. K. CHADHA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, 6, 402.
15. H. M. ROBERG and P. SERVE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1968, 33, 1653.
16. J. A. BARLTROP and B. HESP, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 1625.
17. R. P. GANDHI, S. N. DHAWAN and S. M. MUKHERJI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 283.
18. Unpublished work.
19. A. S. KUSHNER, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1971, 3275.
20. P. DE MAYO and R. W. YIP, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 84.
21. G. O. SCHENCK, I. V. WILUCKI and C. H. KRANCH, *Ber.*, 1962, 95, 1409.
22. G. S. HAMMOND, C. A. STOUT and A. A. LAMOLA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 86, 3103.
23. L. PAOLILLO, H. ZIFFER and O. BUCHARDT, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1970, 35, 38.
24. W. LWOWSKI and J. S. MCCONAGHY, Jr., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 89, 2357, 4450; P. J. WAGNER and G. S. HAMMOND in 'Advances in Photochemistry', (Ed.) W. A. NOYES, G. S. HAMMOND and J. N. PITTS, Interscience, New York, 1968, Vol. 5, p. 35.
25. R. P. GANDHI and MAJAR SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 485.
26. R. P. GANDHI and MAJAR SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 488.
27. R. P. GANDHI, MAJAR SINGH and T. D. SHARMA, *Indian J. Chem.*, (in press).
28. D. BELLUS and P. HRDLJVIC, *Chem. Revs.*, 608, 67, 1967.
29. D. ELAD, D. V. RAO and V. I. STENBERG, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1965, 30, 3252; D. V. RAO and V. LAMBERTI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1967, 32, 2896.
30. Z. HORII, Y. HORI and C. IWATA, *Chem. Comm.*, 1968, 1424.
31. R. W. HOFFMANN and K. R. EICHEN, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1968, 1759.
32. N. C. YANG and G. R. LENZ, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1967, 4897.
33. M. FISCHER, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1968, 4295.
34. R. P. GANDHI, MAJAR SINGH, Y. P. SACHDEVA and S. M. MUKHERJI, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1973, 661.
35. R. P. GANDHI, MAJAR SINGH, Y. P. SCHDEVA and S. M. MUKHERJI, *Chemistry & Industry*, 1973, 382.
36. R. P. GANDHI, MAJAR SINGH, T. D. SHARMA and S. M. MUKHERJI, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1973, 657.
37. G. H. BOOTH and R. G. W. NORRISH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 188.
38. Y. KONDO and B. WITKOP, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 90, 3258.